

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333773706>

Spontaneous Rupture of a Pyogenic Liver Abscess in the Abdominal Wall: a Case Report

Article · May 2019

CITATIONS

0

READS

41

14 authors, including:

Abdourahmane Ndong
Gaston Berger University, Saint-Louis

17 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Jacques Tendeng
Gaston Berger University, Saint-Louis

26 PUBLICATIONS 15 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

M. L. Diao
17 PUBLICATIONS 7 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Philippe Manyacka Ma Nyemb
Gaston Berger University, Saint-Louis

41 PUBLICATIONS 12 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Morphometric project [View project](#)

Radiology [View project](#)

WORLD JOURNAL OF GASTROENTEROLOGY, HEPATOLOGY AND ENDOSCOPY

Spontaneous Rupture of a Pyogenic Liver Abscess in the Abdominal Wall: a Case Report

*Abdourahmane Ndong¹
Jacques Noel Tendeng¹
Fallou Gallas Niang²
Mohamed Lamine Diao¹
Khouidia Kane³
Makhtar Dieng³
Moustapha Diedhiou³
Philippe Manyacka Ma Nyemb¹
Ibrahima Konaté¹

¹Department of General Surgery, University Gaston Berger, Sénégal

²Department of Radiology, Saint-Louis Hospital, Sénégal

³Department of Anesthesiology, Saint-Louis Hospital, Sénégal

Article Information

Article Type: Case Report

Journal Type: Open Access

Volume: 1 **Issue:** 1

Manuscript ID: WJGHE-1-103

Publisher: Science World Publishing

Received Date: 19 April 2019

Accepted Date: 10 May 2019

Published Date: 18 May 2019

***Corresponding author:**

Abdourahmane Ndong

Department of General Surgery
University Gaston Berger
Sénégal

Citation: Abdourahmane Ndong (2019) Spontaneous Rupture of a Pyogenic Liver Abscess in the Abdominal Wall: a Case Report. World J Gastroenterol Hepatol Endosc, 1(1);1-3

Copyright: © 2019, Abdourahmane Ndong, et al., This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

ABSTRACT

Background: Pyogenic liver abscess is defined as a supplicated cavity caused by the invasion and multiplication of bacterial microorganisms in the liver parenchyma. Pyogenic liver abscess rupture in the abdominal wall is rare.

Case Report: We describe a case of spontaneous rupture of a pyogenic liver abscess in the abdominal wall. The computed tomography found a liver abscess of the segment II ruptured in the abdominal wall with an epigastric parietal collection 2.5 cm below the skin. Percutaneous drainage combined with anti-biotherapy was performed favorably.

Conclusion: Rupture in the abdominal wall is a very rare complication of liver abscess. Its prognosis is improved with an early diagnosis by imaging. The best treatment is percutaneous drainage combined with appropriate anti-biotherapy.

KEYWORDS: Liver, Abscess, Pyogenic, Abdominal wall

INTRODUCTION

Pyogenic liver abscess is defined as a supplicated cavity caused by the invasion and multiplication of bacterial microorganisms in the liver parenchyma [1]. Advances in imaging have improved the diagnosis, the treatment and the prognosis [2]. The most common complication is a spontaneous rupture in the abdominal cavity or in the adjacent organs. Rupture in the abdominal wall is rare [3]. We describe a case of spontaneous rupture of a pyogenic liver abscess in the abdominal wall with favorable results after percutaneous drainage and antibiotherapy.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 40-year-old woman, with uncontrolled diabetes was admitted with a 3-week history of pain at the right hypochondrium. These symptoms were associated with swelling of the abdominal wall and a fever, without weight loss, jaundice, or transit disorders. Physical examination showed the following results: a blood pressure of 130/80 mmHg, a body temperature of 38°, a pulse rate of 98/min, a respiratory rate of 22 c/min. On examination an inflammatory epigastric mass was found under shiny skin and was painful to the touch. There were no signs of peritoneal irritation. The rest of the examination was normal. The ultrasound showed the liver abscess content which extends into the abdominal wall, this is shown as a hypoechoic parietal collection. The bile ducts were normal.

The abdominal computed tomography found a 70 x 46 x 38 mm abscess of the segment II of the liver that has ruptured in the abdominal wall and caused an epigastric parietal collection of 84 x 76 x 46 mm 2, 5 cm below the skin (Figure 1 and Figure 2). The blood count showed leukocytosis at 12500/mm³ and anemia at 10.2 g/dL. TP was 88.5% and there was no cholestasis or hepatic cytolysis. There was hypoalbuminemia at 27.4 g/L. This led to the diagnosis of a ruptured liver abscess in the abdominal wall. A percutaneous drainage under local anesthesia was performed which produced 350 cc of pus. A probabilistic antibiotherapy with metronidazole and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid was initiated. The bacteriology found a streptococcus but was not able to determine its group. Over the following 5 days the quantity of pus decreased and the drain dried up on day 5. The follow up abdominal ultrasound performed on day 7 showed a residual hepatic collection estimated at 30 cc. The patient was discharged on day 8. At the 2 month follow-up, the patient had no symptoms.

DISCUSSION

Liver abscess is a serious condition that varies in frequency from country to country [4]. Rupture, which is the main complication, has an estimated frequency between 3.8% and 6.1% [5,6]. It is associated with higher mortality and morbidity [6].

Rupture is most often localized in pleural, peritoneal cavity or septate in the subphrenic right or peripheal regions [7]. The rupture in the pericardial cavity, the mediastinum or the bowel is rare [6]. Rupture in the abdominal wall is rare with few cases reported in the literature [8-10].

Ultrasound and computed tomography play a key role in diagnosis and treatment. They allow the determination of the site of rupture, its size, but also provide guidance for the drainage [11].

Several risk factors of rupture are described in the literature [6]. In our patient, these factors were the diabetes, the bacterial origin, the greater diameter (more than 6 cm) and the localization at the left lobe of the liver.

The unusual localization of the rupture to the abdominal wall can be explained by anatomical factors. The site of the abscess at the left lobe suggests progression to the abdominal wall by the falciform ligament which have with a large lymphatic and arterial network [10,12].

In our case, localization in the anterior portion of segment II near the origin of the falciform ligament could reinforce this hypothesis. Especially since there was no sign of primary cutaneous infection that could lead to purulent parietal collection.

Generally, the rupture of a liver abscess requires a surgical intervention [1]. However, this depends more on the site of rupture. When localized in the pleura, pericardium or abdominal wall, percutaneous drainage with appropriate antibiotherapy may be sufficient [10].

The treatment must be early to avoid the evolution to a secondary rupture in the peritoneal cavity which is a surgical indication. In other situations, fertilization to the skin is possible and have better prognosis [9].

Figure 1: Hypodense collection of the left lobe of the liver in continuity with the abdominal wall (1)

Figure 2: Hypodense collection of the left lobe of the liver in continuity with the abdominal wall (2)

CONCLUSION

Rupture in the abdominal wall is a very rare complication of liver abscess. Its prognosis is improved with an early diagnosis by imaging. The best treatment is percutaneous drainage combined with appropriate antibiotherapy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

None.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

I confirm that none of the authors have any conflict of interest.

FUNDING

Not applicable.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Lardièrre-Deguelte S, Ragot E, Amroun K, Piardi T, Dokmak S, et al. Hepatic abscess: Diagnosis and management. *J Visc Surg*.

- 2015;152(4):231-2S43.
2. Diallo VMPC, Déguénonvo LF, Manga NM, Ka D, Diop SA, et al. Characteristics of Liver Abscess in Department of Infectious Diseases at Fann Teaching University Hospital in Dakar, Senegal. *Adv Infect Dis*. 2018;08:23.
 3. Young AE. The clinical presentation of pyogenic liver abscess. *Br J Surg*. 1976;63(3):216-219.
 4. Huang C, Pitt HA, Lipsett PA, Osterman FA, Lillemoe KD, et al. Pyogenic Hepatic Abscess: Changing Trends Over 42 Years. *Ann Surg*. 1996;223(5):600-609.
 5. Chang Z, Zheng J, Ma Y, Liu Z. Analysis of clinical and CT characteristics of patients with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* liver abscesses: an insight into risk factors of metastatic infection. *Int J Infect Dis*. 2015;33:50-54.
 6. Jun CH, Yoon JH, Wi JW, Park SY, Lee WS, et al. Risk factors and clinical outcomes for spontaneous rupture of pyogenic liver abscess. *J Dig Dis*. 2015;16(1):31-36.
 7. Chen Y-C, Lin C-H, Chang S-N, Shi Z-Y. Epidemiology and clinical outcome of pyogenic liver abscess: an analysis from the National Health Insurance Research Database of Taiwan, 2000-2011. *J Microbiol Immunol Infect*. 2016;49(5):646-653.
 8. Belabbes S. Anterior abdominal wall abscess revealing a pyogenic liver abscess: a case report. *Research*. 2014;1:1256.
 9. Kawoosa NU, Bashir A, Rashid B. Spontaneous Cutaneous Rupture of a Pyogenic Liver Abscess. *Indian J Surg*. 2010;72(4):339-342.
 10. Zizzo M, Zaghi C, Manenti A, Luppi D, Ugoletti L, et al. Abdominal wall abscess secondary to spontaneous rupture of pyogenic liver abscess. *Int J Surg Case Rep*. 2016;25:110-113.
 11. Tasu JP, Moumouh A, Delval O, Hennequin J. L'abcès du foie vu par le radiologue: du diagnostic au traitement. *Gastroenterol Clin Biol*. 2004;28 :477-482.
 12. Warren LR, Chandrasegaram MD, Madigan DJ, Dolan PM, Neo EL, et al. Falciform ligament abscess from left sided portal pyaemia following malignant obstructive cholangitis. *World J Surg Oncol*. 2012;10:278.